

Modeling Dome Seeing in ESO's ELT with Aerothermal Simulations

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Abstract. Besides wavefront distortion due to turbulence of the free atmosphere, temperature fluctuations of the air inside the telescope structure and the dome present major challenges for adaptive optics (AO), often called the Low Wind Effect or, more generally, Dome and Telescope Seeing (DTS). Unfortunately, the magnitude of DTS grows superlinearly with the telescope diameter and can under certain conditions be comparable to, or even larger, than that of the free atmosphere in ESO's ELT.

We present results from transient aerothermal Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations of the entire ESO's ELT telescope, dome, and surrounding air volume. Radiative subcooling to the sky is introduced through appropriate boundary conditions. In particular, the large spiders with total side face area of 723 m² may generate under certain conditions significant spider seeing in form of wavefront "petaling" with induced wavefront discontinuities in the fragmented pupil.

We use *Ansys Fluent* at an outside wind of 5 m/s with directions of 90° and 180° relative to the telescope azimuth. We then execute a transient simulation for a period of about 400 s and trace rays through the 3D temperature field to compute wavefront error maps along the optical path up to the Nasmyth focus. Finally, these maps are fed into a simulation environment that models the propagation of perturbations in an AO control loop, using pyramid wavefront sensing.

We describe the modeling setup including CFD, ray-tracing, and AO analysis, the boundary conditions and their scaling behaviors. Results are presented in terms of time-dependent phase screens and related AO performance analyses for various instances in the parameter space, e.g., CFD boundary conditions, sensing wavelength and control strategy.

Keywords: Dome seeing, Low-Wind Effect, radiative cooling, aerothermal simulations, computational fluid dynamics, end-to-end simulations, ray tracing.

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1 Introduction

Dome and Telescope Seeing (DTS) has been studied as early as 1949 by Couder,¹ who observed variable diffraction spikes due to spiders of the secondary mirror. A large part of DTS is caused by telescope structures having a different, often lower, temperature than the ambient air. The passing air is then cooled, causing a fluctuating thermal wavefront error. Since the magnitude and location of DTS in the pupil depend strongly on the local air speed and direction, and DTS is indeed most prominent at low winds, it is often called the Low Wind Effect.

There have been numerous publications on DTS and aerothermal modeling for the upcoming generation of Extremely Large Telescopes such as for the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT),²⁻¹² the Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT)¹³⁻¹⁹ and the Vera Rubin Telescope (formerly known as LSST).²⁰⁻²³

DTS has been observed at ESO's telescopes and studied in detail in 2018 in the SPHERE planet finder instrument in UT3 of the Very Large Telescope (VLT).^{24,25} In the following years, there have been two in-house modeling studies of DTS in ESO's ELT,²⁶ the first using steady-state aerothermal simulations of the entire Dome and Main Structure (DMS),²⁷ followed by a transient aerothermal study of the M2 crown and top spider only,²⁸ based on the Lattice-Boltzmann Method.

The surface cooling is caused by radiative heat loss to the cold night sky.²⁹ However, as we will see later, thermal inertia of structures can play a large role, and therefore in general all telescope

and dome structures have a variable, nonzero temperature difference relative to the surrounding air at all times. Conversely, any uncooled dissipated heat in the dome such as from motors or bogeys will cause DTS as well.

The upcoming class of extremely large telescopes, and also more and more smaller telescopes, will be assisted by strong adaptive optics (AO). Depending on the instrument, several deformable mirrors may be employed. While these mirrors are normally optimized to correct free atmosphere turbulence, they also mitigate DTS.

Unfortunately, DTS grows quickly with the telescope size. The scaling is faster than linear because even after correcting the (steel) surface area of the dome and main structure (DMS) by the telescope diameter, the spiders and trusses grow in number, become higher (i.e., longer along the optical axis) and also thicker. For example, in ESO's ELT, the total surface area of the six ELT spiders is as large as 723 m², about ten times that of the four VLT spiders (16 m²), even after compensating for the aperture ratio of 38 m / 8 m \approx 5.

Furthermore, as the spiders widen (the shadow growing from 40 mm in the VLT to about 200 mm width in ESO's ELT), they may equal or even exceed Fried's length r_0 . Therefore, spider seeing can exacerbate pupil fragmentation, hence the inability to correctly reconstruct the wavefront across the spider, also known as petaling or the Island Effect.³⁰

A particular challenge for ESO's ELT is the exposed backside of the secondary mirror M2 to the sky (uncoated, etched Zerodur with an emissivity of about 0.9), which strongly cools M2 and indeed, through thermal conduction across the 100 mm thick substrate in the course of hours, generates mirror seeing on the reflective surface.

Figure 1 shows a comparison between free atmosphere seeing and DTS. It becomes obvious that while the two types of optical distortion are of roughly comparable magnitude, they differ in all other properties: DTS tends to be slow and, with the exception of steep Wavefront Error (WFE) spikes at the spider edges, predominantly present at spatial scales of a few meters.

	Free atmosphere seeing	Dome and telescope seeing
conjugation heights	0 to +15 km; but GL dominated (0–1 km?)	Spider: zero, after M1: +/- 3.5 km and more
magnitude (RMS w/o PTT)	$\Delta\phi = 0.058 (D/r_0)^{5/6} \leftrightarrow 0.75 \lambda$ at $r_0 = 20$ cm	Several microns of OPD (\approx 2–3 μ m RMS)
temporal scale	$\tau_0 \approx 2\text{--}5$ ms (0–500 Hz)	≈ 0.5 s (0–2 Hz)
spatial scale	$l_0 \approx$ mm to outer scale $L_0 = 25\text{--}50$ m	Location dependent (cm's to a few m)
power spectral density	Kolmogorov's power law: $k^{-11/3}$	Similar(?), but much smaller inertial subrange
driving factors, properties	C_n^2 profile; telescope state independent (except airmass). Pupil-symmetric, 0 mean	Element dependent (heat, subcooling, wind); Pointing; slit orientation; louvers! Asymmetric

Fig 1 Comparison between free-atmosphere seeing and DTS (GL = ground layer, RMS = root mean square, PTT = piston tip/tilt, OPD = optical path difference)

In order to mitigate the adverse effects of DTS and to increase the air flushing within the telescope chamber, the project has implemented a number of modifications to the Dome and Main Structure including, in particular, a change in the secondary mirror (M2) crown structural design to increase the local air flushing and a reduction of the M2 spider width to reduce the obstruction of the pupil. In addition, the steel beam structure in the Adaptive Relay Tower (ART) and the placement of cabinets, trays, and equipment were optimized to reduce the structural cross section and thus wind shake. Moreover, the project is considering implementing adding louvers (adjustable air vents) in the dome to improve the air flushing of the telescope chamber. In terms of lowering

thermal emissivity of the structural elements, which are close to or within the optical beam, the default is a coating with low-emissivity paint (*LO/MIT-I*), and a cladding with a specific foil with even lower emissivity and reflectivity (*NanoBlack*) is planned for certain structural elements within the optical beam (e.g., the M2 spiders). With CFD modeling becoming more efficient, computers more powerful and strong advances in understanding aerothermal/thermo-optical physics in recent years, AO simulations can more efficiently analyze performance related to DTS and improve algorithms to better correct it. In the following, we describe the CFD models, the data postprocessing and the AO models.

The present study is structured in three parts: The first part encompasses the CFD modeling. Thermal boundary conditions are crucial for these models as they constrain the radiative and convective heat transfer from the structural elements to the sky and from actuators and sensors to the air within the dome, respectively. The definitions of heat sources and heat sinks and their representations in terms of power flow boundary conditions, which are applied to dedicated surfaces and volumes, are discussed in Section 2. The transient aero-thermal CFD models are described in Section 3. The latter yield the three-dimensional temperature distribution within and in the vicinity of the telescope dome for each step of simulated time. The output of the CFD simulations is then interfaced to the data postprocessing, which forms the second part of the study. Here, we perform ray tracing from outside the telescope dome to the telescope focus and interpolate the CFD temperature field to the optical rays. To ensure that we capture the effects of temperature variations at the structural elements and the telescope mirrors, we sample the rays at higher spatial resolution in the vicinity of the structural elements within and close to the optical beam.

We then convert temperature changes to variations of the refractive index and integrate the differential ray segments along the beam propagation down to one of the telescope Nasmyth foci. The integral equals the integrated Optical Path Length (OPL) per ray as a result of temperature deviations relative to the ambient temperature. In a last step, the OPL is interpolated to a regular grid and input to the statistical analyses and the closed-loop AO simulations.

The statistical analyses, studying the wavefront discontinuities in the thermal OPD using a statistical approach, are presented in Section 5. The closed-loop AO simulations, which form the last part of the study, are detailed in Section 6. They evaluate the system-level performance impacts of the thermal OPD by simulating the error propagation through an AO system based the ELT deformable mirror (M4), the fast tip/tilt mirror (M5), and a pyramid wavefront sensor. Performance is evaluated at different sensing wavelengths (I, J, H, and K-Bands) and for a set of seeing conditions ranging from 0.35 to 1.0 arcsec seeing. In addition to exploring the parameter space in terms of seeing and sensing wavelength, two different control strategies are applied: continuous control, which is based on a Karhunen-Loève modal basis, and full control, which enables the control of the wavefront discontinuities present in the thermal OPD.

2 Thermal Boundary Conditions

2.1 Powerflow conditions

Aerothermal simulations are challenging because of the vast range of both, spatial and temporal scales. On the spatial side, a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation needs to span the range from the smallest eddy of millimeter size in the wake of an object like a spider to large vortices the size of the dome. A measure of the degree of turbulence is the Reynolds number $Re = uL/\nu$, where u is the air speed, L a characteristic length such as the width of the dome slit

Fig 2 Structure of the DTS study

and $\nu \approx 1.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ is the kinematic viscosity of air. With Re on the order of a few million, we are in a highly turbulent regime, requiring a very fine simulation grid with about 150 million cells.

Figure 3 shows an overview of the time scales relevant to the CFD. Going from left to right, we start at the smallest, and thus fastest, eddies evolve on a time scale of about 0.1 s. However, when generating OPD movies in the pupil, we find that appreciable differences set on only after about 0.5–1 s, marking the smallest useful period for saving subsequent OPD snapshots. Therefore, from the viewpoint of typical closed-loop AO simulations spanning a few seconds at the most, DTS appears almost static. On the other hand, the thermal OPD maps typically look quite different after several tens of seconds, the time scale of larger blobs of air moving across the telescope beam of size $L \approx 40 \text{ m}$. We thus typically save groups of three subsequent OPD snapshots one second apart, spaced by 60 s intervals.

However, all of these time scales are small compared to thermal inertia of structures like mirror substrates or steel beams. In order to quantify this behavior, it is useful to introduce the convection and conduction time scales

$$t_{\text{conv}} = \frac{E_{\text{th}}}{h_1 + h_2}, \quad t_{\text{cond}} = \frac{w^2}{4\alpha}, \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{t_{\text{conv}}}{t_{\text{cond}}}, \quad (2)$$

where w is the thickness of a slab of a material with thermal diffusivity $\alpha = k/c_m/\rho$, thermal conductivity k , specific heat capacity c_m and specific weight ρ . Some typical thickness values w are 14 mm of steel slabs, 50 mm of Zerodur in the M1 segments and 100 mm in M2. The convective heat exchange coefficients on the two sides of a slab are indicated by h_1 and h_2 . We note that the telescope tube trusses are typically hollow rectangular profiles of mild steel, filled with stagnant air, thus rendering h on the truss inner side very small (see also Fig. 25 in the Appendix).

The symbol $E_{\text{th}} = w k/\alpha$ denotes the specific thermal energy per Kelvin and area of a given structure, which often assumes large values such as 200 kW/K/m² for M2, compared to typical $h_{1,2}$ of 3–10 W/K/m². Therefore, t_{conv} can reach many hours and even span an entire night, several times exceeding t_{cond} even for thick, poor thermal conductors such as Zerodur mirrors (large

ratio γ). Therefore, it is not realistic to assume thermal equilibrium at any time in the dome — instead, spiders and mirrors have nearly always a nonzero temperature offset from the air. Frequently, this offset grows larger in the second half of the night, depending on the ambient temperature evolution and the dome pre-cooling strategy (e.g., targeting thermal equilibrium at sunset vs. at midnight).

Fig 3 Overview of CFD time scales when simulating DTS in ESO's ELT

The large spiders in ESO's ELT with total side face area of 723 m^2 may generate significant spider seeing under certain conditions. The temperature offset of steel structures or mirrors, caused by radiative subcooling to the sky and/or thermal inertia, can be modeled by three different types of boundary condition approaches:

1. A fully coupled radiation/convection/conduction thermal simulation,
2. Constant temperature offset ΔT_{surf} of the surface from ambient, depending on the structural element, its emissivity, sky exposure and local air speed
3. Instead of 2, the local convected power flow, expressed in W/m^2 .

The first method is the only accurate one, including all the relevant physics. Unfortunately, the thermal inertia evolves on time scales many orders slower than any feasible CFD simulation, as indicated in Fig. 3. Therefore, we prefer a simplified, fixed boundary condition, seeking to model a mean state that is reached during a certain period at night. There are two variants of such a boundary condition, as listed above. The convected power flow at any interface equals $h\Delta T_{\text{surf}}$, where the heat transfer coefficient h depends on the local air speed and degree of turbulence.²⁹

In our simulations, we adopted the following scheme: We begin by running an initial CFD simulation with approximate boundary conditions, recording the 3D air speed at each grid point. All simulations run in *Ansys Fluent* and due to the enormous model size, we are limited to single floating point precision. Unfortunately, single precision precludes us from modeling the buoyancy term in air, hence we omit natural convection (which, however, is hopefully negligible at the first quartile outside wind speed of 5 m/s). From the preceding data, we compute h on various surfaces, specifically of the spiders, AR Tower, Top Ring, M2 Crown, mirror substrates etc.

We then obtain accurate cooling powers by running one-dimensional all-night, time-dependent temperature simulations of structures with high thermal inertia such as spider trusses and mirror

Fig 4 Simulated temperature evolution of the 100 mm M2 Zerodur substrate from a transient simulation, spanning an entire night. Top: 1D temperature profile, Bottom: Surface temperature offset from ambient for the top (i.e., sky) and bottom (reflective) surfaces of M2. Peach colored area: out-of-specification region with $\Delta T_{\text{surf}} < -1.5$ K

substrates, as shown in Fig. 4 for the example of M2. The boundary conditions are radiative cooling, specifically on the mirror top side partly exposed to the sky, and the ambient temperature whose evolution is given by the median reference profile specified in ESO’s ELT Environmental Conditions (see Fig. 24 in the Appendix). The M2 substrate is 100 mm thick and made of Zerodur glass ceramic with an etched top side. We model the radiative subcooling on the top side with an emissivity of $\epsilon = 0.9$ and sky view factor of $F_{\text{sky}} = 0.375$. Although Zerodur is a poor thermal conductor, its top side subcooling prints through to the reflective side, where it generates mirror seeing. Both surfaces of M2 are actually subcooled far out of spec ($\Delta T_{\text{surf}} < -1.5$ K) during the last two thirds of the night, assuming median conditions.

We note that any subcooled pocket of air below the reflective side of M2 can have a triple impact on OPD since the telescope beam passes it twice, after which it will likely drift across the M1 pupil, where it crosses the beam a third time.

Finally, we enter power flow boundary conditions in the CFD simulation of magnitude $h\Delta T_{\text{avg}}$ in W/m², where ΔT_{avg} is the surface temperature of a given structure, averaged over the last four hours of the night. The advantage of power flow boundary conditions is that a rather accurate *time averaged* heat power is convected to the air, irrespective of quick fluctuations of the local air speed near a structure. In general, the error in the simulated value of the product $h\Delta T_{\text{avg}}$ is smaller than that of ΔT_{avg} , or h , alone. The disadvantage is that the power flow misses quick variations in h , and thus convected power, due to air speed fluctuations.

2.2 Case study selection

The power flow conditions pertaining to the structural elements, as discussed in Section 2.1, are varied for a number of specific case studies. Because of the large computational effort of CFD simulations on these scales, only three structural configurations and two wind directions were modeled. The following three structural configurations were defined:

- **Case 1: Partial cladding**

Only the top and bottom surfaces of the M2 spiders, the ART spiders and the ART top surfaces are clad with *NanoBlack* foil (10% emissivity),

- **Case 2: Full cladding**

In addition to Case 1, also the side faces are clad with *NanoBlack* foil,

- **Case 3: No cladding**

There is no cladding at all. Instead, all structural surfaces are finished in silvery *LO/MIT-I* (non-Max) paint with 23% emissivity.

Besides the three structural configurations, two wind directions were selected: lateral wind, i.e., wind from 90° azimuth relative to the dome slit, and wind from the back, i.e. 180° azimuth.

Fig 5 The two simulated wind directions. Left: lateral, Right: from the back

2.3 Summary of boundary conditions

CFD-Domain:

- Inlet wind speed: 5 m/s,
- Outlet pressure: 910 hPa (mean environmental air pressure at 3000 m a.s.l.),
- Ambient temperature: 9°C.

The subcooling parameter values are listed in the following tables.

Thermal emissivity epsilon			Sky view factor F _{sky} averaged over respective structure	AVERAGED VALUES Simulated <i>average</i> convective heat transfer coefficients (h,a) of different structures [W/K/m]		Location of structure
Case 1	Case 2	Case 3		Lateral	Back	
				W/K/m2		
						Inside Surfaces
0.03	0.03	0.03	0.40	1.22	1.96	M1 top (reflective) mirror face
0.90	0.90	0.90	0.38	2.78	1.54	M2 top (sky) mirror face
0.90	0.90	0.90	0.38	5.83	2.64	M2 bottom (reflective) mirror face
0.30	0.30	0.30	0.90	2.19	1.77	M2 mount top
0.23	0.23	0.23	0.42	2.89	2.06	M2 mount side
0.23	0.23	0.23	0.50	5.15	3.12	M2 crown
				0.69	1.34	M3 reflective side
0.10	0.10	0.23	0.55	5.02	3.53	Top (M2) spider, top+bottom faces
0.23	0.10	0.23	0.39	4.02	3.06	Top (M2) spider, side faces
0.10	0.10	0.23	0.40	2.69	2.94	ART spider, top+bottom
0.23	0.10	0.23	0.39	2.37	2.63	ART spider, side faces
0.23	0.23	0.23	0.65	3.16	3.27	top ring
0.23	0.23	0.23	0.30	4.33	4.19	STR upper / tubular
0.23	0.23	0.23	0.30	4.89	5.69	LGS baffles
0.85	0.85	0.85	0.15	3.56	7.45	HVAC inside of dome
0.23	0.23	0.23	0.20	1.50	2.12	ART sides
0.10	0.10	0.23	0.75	1.76	2.19	ART top
0.23	0.23	0.23	0.30	1.46	7.28	Cradle inside
0.32	0.32	0.32	0.40	1.97	3.57	M1 Segment crane top+bottom faces
0.23	0.23	0.23	0.39	1.80	3.44	M1 Segment crane side faces
						Dome inner cladding
						Dome floor ("dungeon", transit ring)
						Nasmyth station (i.e., per station)
						Outside Surfaces
0.30	0.30	0.30	0.90	8.45	7.30	outside dome upper region
0.30	0.30	0.30	0.66	7.25	7.98	outside dome lower region
0.63	0.63	0.63	0.66	5.65	6.39	outside dome lower region concrete
0.30	0.30	0.30	0.35	6.36	6.67	Structure below DSD (topview)
0.30	0.30	0.30	1.00	8.34	7.54	wing top
0.30	0.30	0.30	1.00	6.59	8.29	DSD top surface (topview)
0.30	0.30	0.30	0.15	4.80	5.79	aux- entrance-hall (topview)
0.63	0.63	0.63	0.15	5.57	7.28	aux- entrance-hall side concrete

Fig 6 Emissivities, sky-view factors, and local convective heat transfer coefficients.

2.3.1 Heat input during telescope operation

The heat input powers result from the dissipation of instruments, electronic components, drives and hydrostatic bearings, in agreement with the ELT specifications. They are applied as a heat source in a defined volume or as a heat flux on a surface. Figure 8 shows the surface definition of the heat flux in *Ansys Fluent*.

Lateral Wind Case			Back Wind Case			Location of structure
Specific heat flux to air (negative number = air cooling)			Specific heat flux to air (negative number = air cooling)			
Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	
W/m2			W/m2			
						Inside Surfaces
0.93	0.93	0.93	1.13	1.13	1.13	M1 top (reflective) mirror face
-12.21	-12.21	-12.21	-8.29	-8.29	-8.29	M2 top (sky) mirror face
-15.83	-15.83	-15.83	-10.08	-10.08	-10.08	M2 bottom (reflective) mirror face
-16.10	-16.10	-16.10	-12.72	-12.72	-12.72	M2 mount top
-5.76	-5.76	-5.76	-4.56	-4.56	-4.56	M2 mount side
-8.32	-8.32	-8.32	-6.89	-6.89	-6.89	M2 crown
-1.26	-1.26	-1.26	-1.30	-1.30	-1.30	M3 reflective side
-2.81	-2.81	-8.56	-2.52	-2.52	-7.71	Top (M2) spider, top+bottom faces
-5.15	-0.74	-5.15	-4.43	-0.52	-4.43	Top (M2) spider, side faces
-2.04	-2.04	-6.23	-1.83	-1.83	-5.61	ART spider, top+bottom
-5.15	-0.74	-5.15	-4.43	-0.52	-4.43	ART spider, side faces
-10.12	-10.12	-10.12	-9.11	-9.11	-9.11	top ring
-3.96	-3.96	-3.96	-3.41	-3.41	-3.41	STR upper / tubular
-1.57	-1.57	-1.57	-1.41	-1.41	-1.41	LGS baffles
-7.32	-7.32	-7.32	-6.30	-6.30	-6.30	HVAC inside of dome
-5.15	-5.15	-5.15	-2.27	-2.27	-2.27	ART sides
-2.04	-2.04	-6.23	-3.44	-3.44	-10.51	ART top
-3.00	-3.00	-3.00	-3.00	-3.00	-3.00	Cradle inside
-6.54	-6.54	-6.54	-5.86	-5.86	-5.86	M1 Segment crane top+bottom faces
-5.15	-5.15	-5.15	-4.43	-4.43	-4.43	M1 Segment crane side faces
-110 kW	-110 kW	-110 kW	-110 kW	-110 kW	-110 kW	Dome inner cladding
-98.4 kW	-98.4 kW	-98.4 kW	-98.4 kW	-98.4 kW	-98.4 kW	Dome floor ("dungeon", transit ring)
-14.5 kW	-14.5 kW	-14.5 kW	-14.5 kW	-14.5 kW	-14.5 kW	Nasmyth station (i.e., per station)
						Outside Surfaces
-27.5	-27.5	-27.5	-27.5	-27.5	-27.5	outside dome upper region
-20.2	-20.2	-20.2	-20.2	-20.2	-20.2	outside dome lower region
-42.4	-42.4	-42.4	-42.4	-42.4	-42.4	outside dome lower region concrete
-10.7	-10.7	-10.7	-10.7	-10.7	-10.7	Structure below DSD (topview)
-30.6	-30.6	-30.6	-30.6	-30.6	-30.6	wing top
-30.6	-30.6	-30.6	-30.6	-30.6	-30.6	DSD top surface (topview)
-4.6	-4.6	-4.6	-4.6	-4.6	-4.6	aux- entrance-hall (topview)
-9.6	-9.6	-9.6	-9.6	-9.6	-9.6	aux- entrance-hall side concrete

Fig 7 Local heat fluxes for lateral and back wind configurations.

3 Computational Fluid Dynamics Simulations

Transient aerothermal CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) simulations of the entire ESO Extremely Large Telescope have been carried out. The CFD model consists of the dome with open louvers and undeployed windscreen. Inside is the main structure at an altitude angle of 60°, the ART tower, spiders, mirrors, the HVAC system and the Nasmyth platforms with instruments. The

Table 1 Heat input during telescope operation

Structure name	Heat power [W]
M1 Subcell (M1 support with edge sensors and actuators)	9460
M1 Truss (cabinets at M1 floor)	2150
Instrument A	500
Instrument B	500
M2 brakes	90
M2 cabinets	180
M3 brakes	60
M3 electric	160
Cabinets at intermediate platform (below Nasmyth)	200
Altitude Drives	1000
Azimuth Drives	5000
Hydrostatic Bearings Azimuth	10000
Hydrostatic Bearings Altitude	1000

Fig 8 Example of boundary heat loss

surrounding air volume was chosen according to the specifications for external building aerodynamics. The shape of the Cerro Armazones was not considered. The CFD models in Ansys Fluent were created for wind directions of 90° (lateral wind) or 180° (back wind) relative to the azimuth of the telescope. Due to the high geometric complexity of the model, which includes tens of thousands of surfaces, simplifications were made and complex components were represented with porous media. Porous media models were applied to specific components that are impractical to resolve directly within the global model such as the M1 subcell with mirror actuators, the honeycomb structure below the M1 Cell, the M1 floor (a support plate with very small perforations), the M3 trapdoor, the Nasmyth platform instruments, the undeployed windscreen, the truss structure

below the dome gate, etc. These porous media representations were calibrated using independent local high-fidelity CFD models for each component. Calibration was performed at different air speeds and flow directions. Figures 9 and 10 show the dome in the construction phase and the corresponding CFD model.

An auxiliary volume, representing the entire beam path, has been integrated into the CFD model in order to significantly accelerate the transfer of results to the OPD calculation. The meshing was performed using *Fluent Mosaic*. The resulting meshes contain approximately 150 million cells. To capture flow separation with high accuracy and improved flexibility with respect to the wall treatment ($y+$ values), the two-equation $k-\Omega$ SST turbulence model has been adopted. We validated that a sufficient resolution of the flow in the viscous sublayer with $y+$ values of around unity has been achieved in regions of the optical path and specific flow importance such as near louvers. These regions often require a very fine boundary layer mesh. Typically, 10 elements per layer were used and the mesh size in the volume of the optical beams equals 0.3 m.

According to the ELT specifications, an atmospheric boundary layer is required at the inlet of the area. The inlet flow velocity is 5 m/s, corresponding to the first quartile of measured wind velocities on Cerro Armazones. The thermal boundary conditions are subcooling and heat dissipation from instruments or electrical/mechanical components during operation. Subcooling denotes the radiative cooling of the dome and of the main structure against the cold night sky. Heat dissipation is the fraction of the heat input to the DMS, mainly from instruments, cabinets, drives and hydrostatic bearings not removed by water cooling. These heat loads are obtained from specifications.

The simulation is initially run in steady state mode to obtain a reasonably converged solution from which a transient simulation is then initiated. After allowing the model to evolve for 270 s to eliminate initial transients, time-dependent solutions are recorded for post-processing. Three groups of three snapshots each of temperature results, spaced by 1 s, respectively, are recorded for the OPD calculation, spaced by 60 s intervals.

Figures 11 and 12 show the simulated air temperature inside the dome for load CASE01 and CASE02 at a selecting cutting plane, respectively.

Fig 9 Dome and main structure in the construction phase (photo taken in January 2025)

Fig 10 Dome and main structure in the CFD model

4 CFD data postprocessing

In the next step, we trace rays through the 3D temperature field to compute wavefront error maps along the optical path up to the Nasmyth focus. Using in-house developed ray tracing software, a grid of rays is generated and traced through the ELT, so that intersection points are determined between the rays and each of the five mirrors. Such a ray bundle is representative of a point source at infinity at a specific field location. From the CFD, the temperature at every grid point of the mesh is loaded and interpolated to the sample points along the rays.

Figure 13 shows the lateral sampling of the ray positions in the ELT entrance pupil plane with about 50,000 rays. The lateral ray density is higher in the vicinity of the spider arm surfaces to better resolve regions of high spatial OPD gradient.

Longitudinally, the sampling starts about 30 m above the telescope and finishes at one of the Nasmyth foci. Sample points with a separation of 50 mm are generated along each ray. Below 0.3 m distance from the mirrors, the longitudinal sampling is refined to 1 mm spacing to better resolve mirror seeing.

The gradient dn/dT of refractive index with temperature at the median conditions on Cerro Armazones with an air pressure of 710 hPa, ambient night temperature of 9 °C and relative humidity (RH) of 7% is computed from the formulae in ³¹ resulting in the easy to remember value of -700 nm/K/m at the wavelength of $2.2 \mu\text{m}$ (K-band). Since the dependence on RH and wavelength is quite small, we employ this number as a fixed value in our simulations (however, note that dn/dT is proportional to air pressure and mildly temperature dependent, changing to -743 nm/K/m at $T = 0^\circ\text{C}$).

The differential OPL, or OPD, is integrated along the rays. The main result is the accumulated OPL for each ray in the pupil plane, but we also store the OPL along each ray, so that critical locations in the telescope with much OPD variation among nearby rays can be identified and studied in the post-processing.

Fig 11 Lateral wind CASE01 (partial cladding): Temperature difference parallel to symmetry plane at 100 mm offset from the spider surface

The integrated OPL results in the image plane are further interpolated to the pixel scale of a given wavefront sensor. Several ray bundles are generated at different field points. In contrast to providing phase screens at various places in the telescope dome (i.e., planes across the optical beam train), as is customary when simulating turbulent layers in the free atmosphere at multiple heights, we prefer computing the integrated OPL at selected field points as a more direct and accurate approach, because it avoids interpolations on various intermediate planes along the telescope beam with strongly varying footprints and orientations. The resulting integrated OPL maps are then input to the adaptive optics simulations, as presented in the following section.

5 Analysis of OPD map features: RMS, PtV, discontinuity

This section presents a brief analysis of some properties of the thermo-OPD maps. In addition to classical metrics like Peak-To-Valley, fitting error with the M4 corrector, we characterize the WF discontinuities. The notion of sharp discontinuity has been introduced by³² as a nonzero curl wavefront (WF) presenting a constant discontinuity along each side of a spider arm. One of the six modes, called θ -mode because it describes the azimuthal angle function, is represented in Fig. 14. We concentrate our analysis on these modes, as they are responsible for instabilities in AO loops, especially for pyramid sensors at short wavelength in the presence of bad seeing. Other

Fig 12 Lateral wind CASE02 (full cladding): Temperature difference parallel to symmetry plane at 100 mm offset from the spider surface

discontinuities exist, like for instance in-sector tip-tilt, but those are well identified by the sensor and not studied here.

5.1 Definition of discontinuity in presence of spider arms

One difficulty for the analysis is that even a continuous WF, considering just the free-atmosphere turbulence and an iso-thermal telescope, will in general cause a step across the spider, as illustrated in Fig. 15. This step δ_{iso} is usually small enough to be handled by imposing a null difference of the AO correction between the spider sides (see Section 6). However, in case of a non-isothermal telescope, spider seeing induces a much stronger WF step that can no longer be ignored (δ_{lwe} in Fig. 15).

We propose estimating δ_{lwe} in terms of modal coefficients of discontinuity modes describing the deviation from a continuous WF. In order to cope with the unknown WF in the spider arm shadow, we use a statistical approach to estimate a "continuous" projection of the thermo-OPD maps that we analyze.

5.2 Algorithm for the estimation of the discontinuity

By combining the six θ -modes, we can define an orthonormal basis, composed of the "windmill mode" (sum of all θ -modes) and five petal modes that are composed of differential piston-in-sectors

Fig 13 Sampling of ray positions across the entrance pupil with higher resolution around the spiders

Fig 14 Sharp discontinuity θ -mode.

(see Fig. 16, where KL stands for Karhunen-Loève).

We define the following variables:

- m : Real modal coefficients (least-squares projection of WF on basis),
- m' : Extrapolated coefficients using a smooth regularization (continuity-like constraint),
- T_m : Uncertainty matrix (or trust matrix),
- L : Laplacian regularization matrix,
- α : Hyper-parameter.

The extrapolation is obtained by defining the matrix E_m such that $m' = E_m m$ yields a set of coefficients describing a smoothed version of the thermo-OPD map (minimizing local Laplacian).

Fig 15 Illustration of WF discontinuities. The blue rectangle represents the cross section of a spider arm. The green line is a continuous WF typical of atmospheric turbulence and low-order dome seeing for an isothermal telescope structure. The dashed green curve represents the WF before it intersects the spider. The red line is the WF in the case of a non-isothermal telescope with spider seeing.

Fig 16 Modal basis: 6 discontinuity modes (windmill mode + 5 petal modes), plus 3000 KL-modes.

The coefficients m describing the thermal-OPD map ϕ are given by

$$m = \frac{1}{n_p} B^T H^T \phi, \quad (3)$$

where $\phi[n_p]$ is the vector of n_p values of the discretized map to analyze. Then $B[n_{\text{act}}, n_{\text{modes}}]$ is the modal basis and $H[n_p, n_{\text{act}}]$ is the DM influence matrix, where $n_{\text{act}} = 5352$ is the number of actuators on M4.

We formulate a maximum a-posteriori problem, where the unknown coefficients m' are assumed to be described by a covariance matrix L^{-1} obtained from a k^{-4} power law, where k is the spatial frequency (L is the Laplacian, whose power law happens to be close to Kolmogorov's of $k^{-11/3}$). The symbol T_m denotes a diagonal covariance matrix of the uncertainty in the modal coefficients. From Bayes' theorem, we can write the following conditional probability:³³

$$P(m'|m) = \frac{P(m') P(m|m')}{P(m)}, \quad (4)$$

where $P(m)$ equals unity, because these coefficients are known exactly. Then by expressing Eq. (4) for Gaussian variables, we obtain

$$P(m'|m) \simeq \exp \left[- \left(m'^T L m' + (m - m')^T T_m^{-1} (m - m') \right) / 2 \right]. \quad (5)$$

The minimization of the logarithm of $P(m'|m)$ yields the matrix E_m , where we have introduced the hyper-parameter α for weighting the regularization

$$E_m = (T_m^{-1} + \alpha L)^{-1} T_m^{-1}. \quad (6)$$

The uncertainty matrix T_m represents the error on the modal coefficient estimation. We adapt this matrix in order to impose that only the six first discontinuity modes are determined and produce a smooth WF. We thus set T_m to

$$\text{diag}(T_m)_{1..6} = 10^{-3}, \quad (7)$$

$$\text{diag}(T_m)_{7..3006} = 10^{-9}. \quad (8)$$

We impose that the six discontinuity modes are only known with an uncertainty of 1 mm (effectively arbitrarily large), hence they will be predicted purely from the statistics described by L and tuned to obtain a nearly continuous wavefront. The rest of the modes is supposed to be known at nanometer precision, such that they will not be altered by the extrapolation. To adjust the estimation matrix, we tune the hyper-parameter α and check on continuous atmospheric-like screens that we are correctly evaluating the six first coefficients of m' . Figure 17 shows the real temporal evolution of the coefficient of one of the petal modes in comparison with the extrapolated ones.

Fig 17 Temporal evolution of petal mode #1 coefficient (blue) and estimation from continuous extrapolation.

Fig 18 Left: Map corresponding to the projection m of the the thermo-OPD on the overall basis. Right: Map of the continuous projection m' . The difference yields an approximate representation of the discontinuity due to DTS.

We apply the method to thermo-OPD screens and show one example in Fig. 18. Two phase screens are computed from the coefficients m (the real projection) and m' (the continuous projection). The difference between these two maps equals the discontinuities (components limited to the six discontinuity modes). We estimate the precision on the reconstructed petal components to be of the order of 5% because of the unknown part of the seeing WFE obscured by the spiders and because of potential cross-talk with other non-estimated discontinuous features (e.g., tip-tilt within sectors).

5.3 Results

We study lateral wind and back wind. For each wind direction, two cases are considered:

Case 1: Partial cladding. Case 2: Full cladding. For each case, groups of 3 time steps, separated by 60 s, are extracted. We analyze the overall RMS of the WF, the fitting error after correcting all 3006 modes and the discontinuities represented in terms of maps of WF difference as in Fig. 18. The Peak-To-Valley (PTV) and RMS errors of the discontinuities are given in Figs. 30–35 in the Appendix. In Table 19, we present a summary of the results. Note that we also indicate for the discontinuities the Peak-To-Mean (PTM) excursion with respect to the WF, which is a more useful measure of the phase excursion in case of single outlier petal, while the PTV is more representative of two neighboring petals with large amplitude and opposite signs. We find that the side wind generates a much larger overall RMS error than the back wind case. However, in all cases we observe a small fitting error of the order of 10 to 20 nm, so these features are not challenging.

The discontinuities are more problematic: They are slightly larger for the back wind than for the side wind. The full cladding has a clear advantage and indeed reduces the discontinuities by half. But even for the full cladding, the discontinuities are far from being negligible, especially for AO systems at short sensing wavelengths (order $\lambda_{\text{WFS}}/2$ ($\lambda_{\text{WFS}}/4$) in R-band).

	Side Wind	Back Wind
RMS full dome seeing		
Partial Cladding	2.93 μm	0.67 μm
Full Cladding	2.86 μm	0.64 μm
RMS fitting error		
Partial Cladding	23.4 nm	13.7 nm
Full Cladding	18.4 nm	10.2 nm
Discontinuity PTV (PTM)		
Partial Cladding	624 nm (378 nm)	777 nm (470 nm)
Full Cladding	313 nm (173 nm)	387 nm (251 nm)

Fig 19 Summary of RMS WFE and its fitting errors

6 AO simulations

We ran end-to-end simulations to evaluate the impact of DTS on the wavefront quality delivered after AO correction.

The OPD maps (see Section 4) were fed into a simulation environment modeling the propagation of perturbations in an AO control loop. This study was limited to analyzing the performance

impact in the context of an Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics (SCAO) system observing a bright (i.e., zero photon noise) Natural Guide Star with a Pyramid Wavefront Sensor.

6.1 Temporal decoupling of dome seeing and AO process

The results of the CFD simulations suggest a time scale of the dome seeing variations of several tens of seconds, while the AO controller rejection bandwidth is ~ 30 Hz. The two processes can therefore be considered decoupled and a static dome seeing wavefront map is added to the free-atmosphere seeing model in each of the AO simulations.

6.2 Parameter space

A Pyramid WFS model has been selected for its capacity to detect the petal modes, yet limited to conditions where the residual wavefront errors are within its linear regime, i.e., λ_{WFS} . To explore the transition between the linear and nonlinear regimes, the simulations were repeated for the following parameter combinations:

- sensing wavelengths: I (800 nm), J (1200 nm), H (1650 nm) and K-bands (2200 nm),
- free atmosphere seeing (defined at $\lambda = 500 \text{ nm}$ and zenith): 0.35, 0.5, 0.65, 0.8 and 1 arcsec at 30° zenith angle with a wind speed of 10 m/s (valid at the free-atmosphere phase screens).

Possible correlations between the dome seeing and the free atmosphere seeing, e.g. through wind speed or direction, have not been considered.

6.3 AO model

The pyramid parameters were those of the ELT PDS baseline (96 pixels per quadrant, 0.428 m/pixel when projected onto the pupil, modulation radius = $3\lambda_{\text{WFS}}/D$).

A basis of 3000 KL-modes was built with a continuity constraint across the boundaries between the six pupil sectors: The modes were first sampled on a virtual Deformable Mirror (DM) covering the footprint of M1 on M4 when observing on axis, where the pairs of adjacent actuators along the petal edges were replaced by their midpoints (Fig. 20). The modes were then resampled at the actuator locations on the real DM under the assumption of Kolmogorov's power law.

In addition, six θ -modes are fitted with the 3000 KL-modes and their fitting errors, called discontinuity modes (Fig. 21), added to the modal basis. The discontinuity modes are thus orthogonal to the KL-basis and provide control over the petal modes when added to the KL-basis.

We tested two control strategies:

- *continuous*: modal basis is limited to the 3000-KL modes,
- *full control*: the KL-mode basis is complemented by six θ discontinuity modes.

Fig 20 Modal basis sampling: the M1 on-axis footprint (black hexagons) is shown on top of the M4 actuators positions (gray hexagons). Illuminated actuators (blue dots) and midpoints (red dots) of pairs of adjacent actuators along the petal edges are used to generate the continuous basis.

Fig 21 Left: one of the six θ -modes equal to the azimuthal coordinate wrapped at the angle of one of the petal edges. The difference between two consecutive θ -modes is a petal piston mode. Right: discontinuity mode equal to the fitting error of the θ -mode on the 3000 KL-modes.

6.4 Optical gain compensation

The optical gains are compensated in Fourier space with a look-up table derived from a convolution model^{34,35} computed at the applied free-atmosphere seeing for the AO control parameters.

The optical gain compensation is inaccurate during the convergence of the AO loop, when the residual WF error is larger than in steady state. When the petal modes are controlled, the transient may occasionally converge to a solution with $2\pi n$ phase errors along some of the petal piston modes, where n is a small integer. This convergence error was kept outside the scope of the study by an ad-hoc removal of $2\pi n$ petal errors after 500 ms.

Fig 22 Top: Intra-sector performance: K-band Strehl ratios obtained with the four sensing wavelengths for five tested free atmosphere seeing values (x -axis). For each seeing value, two groups of bars are shown for the two control strategies (blue = continuous, red = with petal modes). For each control strategy, the results are shown for three telescope configurations; from left to right: no cladding, partial cladding, full cladding. The light green background indicates the performance with the isothermal telescope (i.e., no dome seeing applied). Bottom: Full-pupil performance with black line rectangles marking the intra-sector performance of the isothermal telescope.

6.5 Performance metrics

The performance metric is the integrated K-band Strehl ratio derived from the residual wavefront error using the Maréchal approximation:

- over the full telescope aperture (full-pupil performance),
- over each of the six pupil sectors (intra-sector performance).

The period of each simulation was 5 s and the performance metrics were averaged over the last 2.5 s.

6.6 Simulation results

6.6.1 Intra-sector performance

The intra-sector performance (Fig. 22 top) is independent of the control strategy and only weakly affected by the presence of dome seeing. Due to the loss of linearity of the WFS when the residual WFE exceeds $\sim \lambda_{\text{WFS}}/4$, and despite the compensation of the optical gains, the AO performance degrades at short sensing wavelengths and mediocre seeing.

These results suggest that DTS does not substantially affect the intra-sector performance.

6.6.2 Full-pupil performance

The full-pupil performance is shown in Fig. 22, bottom. At infrared sensing wavelengths (H and K-bands), the performance of the isothermal telescope is nearly restored for all telescope configurations and control strategies, yet with a small benefit of combining the full-cladding with the full control strategy (i.e., with petal modes included). However, the performance collapses completely when controlling the petal modes with wavefront residuals larger than $\sim \lambda_{\text{WFS}}/5$ (I-band at seeing ≥ 0.65 arcsec, J-band at seeing ≥ 1 arcsec). Under these degraded conditions, the continuous control strategy mitigates the impact, with a residual performance penalty strongly dependent on the telescope configuration, suggesting a substantial benefit of implementing the full cladding solution.

7 Discussion and Conclusions

This work presents aerothermal Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations of the entire dome and main structure of ESO's ELT and AO performance analyses of the effects of thermally induced OPD. The sampling of the parameter space was mainly constrained by CFD computational effort. We executed six case studies: three structural surface configurations with two wind directions each. In a second stage, the six CFD case studies were input to AO simulations that evaluated performance at four sensing wavelengths, two control strategies and five seeing conditions, resulting in a total of 240 combinations.

The simulations described above show that DTS is characterized by a relatively strong OPD (2–3 μm RMS), although the associated aberrations are spatially low order and evolve slowly (seconds to tens of seconds). This behavior is in rough agreement with our initial CFD studies.^{27,28}

The impact of DTS tends to diminish during the first part of the night, as ambient temperatures usually drop, reducing thermal gradients within the dome between the ambient air and the subcooled structural elements. However, this partial masking effect stops as soon as the ambient temperature settles and can be reversed once the ambient temperatures increase.

The effect of DTS is dominated by spider and mirror seeing from M1 and M2, with limited additional OPD introduced beyond M2. DTS often causes significant, persistent, and asymmetric OPD steps across the spiders.

While the ELT deformable mirror with its six independently movable petals can effectively correct petal modes, the sharp OPD gradients near the spider edges cannot be corrected. However, their local contribution to the overall RMS wavefront error remains at a level of 15 nm RMS, as the fitting error analysis has shown (Section 5.3).

To summarize, we conclude that DTS is:

1. powerful (2–3 μm RMS), but spatially low order and slow,
2. additive to the free-atmosphere seeing and mostly independent of it,
3. mitigated when the ambient temperature drops during the night,
4. dominated by spider seeing and M1, M2 mirror seeing (little incremental OPD after M2),
5. causing significant, slowly varying and asymmetric OPD steps across the spiders,
6. suffering from sharp spikes near the spider edges which, however, only have small influence on the total WFE (global fitting error about 15 nm RMS).

The Single Conjugate AO (SCAO) analyses at various seeing conditions and sensing wavelengths indicate that performance is only weakly affected in H and K-bands, up to a seeing of at least 1.0 arcsec. At these sensing wavelengths the performance even in the no-cladding case is acceptable. In the I and J-Bands, however, the performance is strongly affected even with partial cladding, except under excellent seeing conditions and with a dedicated control strategy. Only in the full-cladding case, the performance loss is acceptable under all seeing conditions.

As the performance analyses were done in SCAO mode only, hence on axis, residual field-dependent errors remain to be studied. Because thermal OPD is generated at various places within the telescope structure, and thus along the optical path, its effect is optically conjugated to a wide range of altitudes so that field-dependent effects may become relevant for wide-field instruments and AO modules with secondary deformable mirrors. For this reason, we propose complementing the CFD postprocessing with OPD interpolations for each line of sight separately.

References

- 1 A. Couder, “Sur un Effet Thermique Observé dans les Télescopes a Réflexion,” *L’Astronomie* **63**, 253–258 (1949).
- 2 “Thirty Meter Telescope International Observatory website.” <http://www.tmt.org>.
- 3 K. Vogiatzis and G. Z. Angeli, “Strategies for estimating mirror and dome seeing for TMT,” *Proc. SPIE* **6271**, 27 (2006).

- 4 K. Vogiatzis and R. Upton, “TMT studies on thermal seeing modeling: Mirror and dome seeing model validation,” *Proc. SPIE* **6271**, 48 (2006).
- 5 J. Pazder and K. Vogiatzis, “Dome and mirror seeing estimates for the Thirty Meter Telescope,” *Proc. SPIE* **7017**, 26 (2008).
- 6 K. Vogiatzis, “Thermal modeling environment for TMT,” *Proc. SPIE* **7738**, 11 (2010).
- 7 K. Vogiatzis, “Aerothermal modeling framework for TMT,” in *Proceedings of the Integrated Modeling of Complex Optomechanical Systems*, **8336**, 10, SPIE, (Kiruna, Sweden) (2011).
- 8 K. Vogiatzis, A. Sadjadjpour, and S. Roberts, “TMT telescope structure thermal model,” *Proc. SPIE* **9150**, 72 (2014).
- 9 K. Vogiatzis, “Transient aero-thermal simulations for TMT,” in *Proc. SPIE*, **9150**, 24 (2014).
- 10 K. Vogiatzis and H. Thompson, “On the precision of aero-thermal modeling for TMT,” *Proc. SPIE* **9911**, 40 (2016).
- 11 K. Vogiatzis, H. Thompson, and S. Roberts, “On the precision of aero-thermal simulations for TMT: Revisited,” in *Proc. SPIE*, **10705**, 4 (2018).
- 12 K. Vogiatzis, D. MacMartin, L. Wang, *et al.*, “The TMT International Observatory aerothermal performance estimation procedure,” *Proc. SPIE* **13099**, 100 (2024).
- 13 “Giant Magellan Telescope.” <http://giantmagellan.org> website.
- 14 K. Das, K. Vogiatzis, G. Z. Angeli, *et al.*, “GMT aerothermal modeling validation through site measurement,” *Proc. SPIE* **10705**, 2 (2018).
- 15 K. Vogiatzis, K. Das, G. Z. Angeli, *et al.*, “Computational Fluid Dynamics Modeling of GMT,” *Proc. SPIE* **10705**, 28 (2018).
- 16 K. Vogiatzis, K. Das, B. Sitariski, *et al.*, “Using a stochastic approach to estimate the aerothermal performance of the Giant Magellan Telescope,” in *AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting*, 2019–2319, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, (Reston, VA, USA) (2019).
- 17 R. Conan, M. van Dam, K. Vogiatzis, *et al.*, “Modeling the Giant Magellan Telescope dome seeing using fluid dynamics simulations,” in *Proceedings of the AO4ELT6*, (Quebec City, QC, Canada) (2019).
- 18 K. Vogiatzis, H. Fitzpatrick, K. Das, *et al.*, “Aerothermal modeling for design support, requirement validation and performance assessment of GMT subsystems,” *Proc. SPIE* **12187**, 22 (2022).
- 19 K. Vogiatzis, H. Fitzpatrick, R. Conan, *et al.*, “GMT primary mirror thermal control system and thermal deformation modeling framework,” *Proc. SPIE* **13099**, 102 (2024).
- 20 “Vera C. Rubin Observatory website.” <http://rubinobservatory.org/>.
- 21 J. Sebag, K. Vogiatzis, J. Barr, *et al.*, “LSST summit enclosure: Facility design optimization using aero-thermal modeling,” *Proc. SPIE* **8449**, 3 (2012).
- 22 J. Sebag and K. Vogiatzis, “Estimating dome seeing for LSST,” *Proc. SPIE* **9150**, 26 (2014).
- 23 K. Vogiatzis, B. Xin, C. Claver, *et al.*, “Dome seeing sensitivity analysis for LSST,” *Proc. SPIE* **10705**, 3 (2018).
- 24 J. Milli, M. Kasper, P. Bourget, *et al.*, “Low wind effect on VLT/SPHERE: impact, mitigation strategy, and results,” *Proc. SPIE* **10703**, 107032A (2018).
- 25 M. Wilby, C. Keller, J.-F. Sauvage, *et al.*, “Laboratory verification of Fast Furious phase diversity: Towards controlling the low wind effect in the SPHERE instrument,” *Astron. & Astrophys.* **615**(A34) (2018).

- 26 “European Extremely Large Telescope website.” <http://elt.eso.org>.
- 27 R. Holzlöhner and M. Brinkmann, “Mitigating wavefront error caused by sky subcooling of the ELT structure,” *Proc. SPIE* **11445**, 114450Y (2020).
- 28 D. Martins, R. Holzlöhner, C. Verinaud, *et al.*, “Transient wavefront error from cooled air downwind of telescope spiders,” *Proc. SPIE* **12187**, 1218712 (2022).
- 29 A. Holzlöhner, S. Kimeswenger, W. Kausch, *et al.*, “Bolometric night sky temperature and subcooling of telescope structures,” *Astron. & Astrophys.* **645**, A32 (2021).
- 30 S. Bonnefond, M. Tallon, M. Le Louarn, *et al.*, “Wavefront reconstruction with pupil fragmentation: study of a simple case,” *Proc. SPIE* **9909**, 990972 (2016).
- 31 G. Bönsch and E. Potulski, “Measurement of the refractive index of air and comparison with modified Edlén’s formulae,” *Metrologia* **35**, 133 (1998).
- 32 N. Pourré, J. B. Le Bouquin, J. Milli, *et al.*, “Low-wind-effect impact on Shack-Hartmann-based adaptive optics. Partial control solution in the context of SPHERE and GRAVITY+,” **665**, A158 (2022).
- 33 G. Rousset, *Wave-front sensors*, ch. 5, 91–130. Cambridge University Press (1999).
- 34 Chambouleyron, V., Fauvarque, O., Janin-Potiron, P., *et al.*, “Pyramid wavefront sensor optical gains compensation using a convolutional model,” **644**, A6 (2020).
- 35 O. Fauvarque, P. Janin-Potiron, C. Correia, *et al.*, “Kernel formalism applied to Fourier-based wave-front sensing in presence of residual phases,” *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A* **36**, 1241–1251 (2019).

Disclosures

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Code, Data, and Materials Availability

The simulation results are being made available to the instrument consortia.

The authors are engineers/physicists working for the European Southern Observatory (ESO) in Garching near Munich, Germany.

Biographies and photographs of the authors are not available.

8 Appendix

8.1 Computation of radiative cooling powers

In order to compute the radiative subcooling of various structures of limited size, we employed the "bottom-up" method as discussed in Section 2 and defined in.²⁹ The only two quantities to be determined for each surface are thus the emissivity ϵ and the sky view factor F_{sky} , the latter representing the solid angle fraction of sky seen from the surface, relative that of the full hemisphere, times the direction cosine to the surface normal.

For extended structures such as the telescope floor and inner dome cladding, this approach is less useful because it would entail subdividing the surfaces into many small sections. Instead, we use the "top-down" approach, a Monte Carlo sampling method in which we pick random points across the curved, virtual open slit surface (size about $43 \text{ m} \times 70 \text{ m}$ at 30° zenith angle), for each point consider a thermal radiation ray with random k -vector (selected from a cosine distribution, hence preferentially oriented near normal to the local tangential plane on the dome slit surface), and trace the ray into the dome. Each ray may strike the dome interior directly (Fig. 23 a,b), or else reflect off M1 beforehand (c), hit the dome floor and so forth. We differentiate seven different ray path categories, listed in the Table d) with their associated cooling powers.

When summing the cooling powers of the seven ray categories, we consider a different emissivity for each, depending on the type of end point material. We assume that a partially reflected ray will continue and is likely to strike the interior of the dome again. However, while the cooling will, in general, be distributed over several ray intersection points with various surfaces, we mostly care about the net thermal effect and lump all the power into the first intersection with a mostly absorptive material, like the inner dome cladding. We adopt the detailed sky cooling model derived in,²⁹ hence take into account that the bolometric sky temperature is lower sky at smaller zenith angles.

The simplified result is that the inside dome cladding and the floor are cooled with a power of about 125 kW each in the ELT. The cooling on these surfaces is rather uniformly distributed. These cooling powers are then added to the power flow boundary conditions in *Ansys Fluent*.

8.2 Details of the "all-night" transient temperature simulations

The "all-night" transient temperature simulations shown in Fig. 4 were carried out with the median reference temperature profile, but we have a large database of measured temperature profiles on Cerro Armazones, five of which are shown by the colored curves in Fig. 24. In general, falling ambient temperature tends to mitigate radiative subcooling, therefore, the T_{amb} are important environmental parameters and play a role in determining the achievable image quality during an actual telescope night.

The table in Fig. 25 shows various surface elements identified in Fig. 6, their slab thicknesses w , two-sided convection coefficients $h_{1,2}$, emissivity ϵ , sky view factor F_{sky} , ancillary static temperature offsets $\Delta T_{\text{top,bot}}$ and materials. The last four columns yield the surface temperature offsets from local ambient and their product, the convected powers $P_{\text{conv}} = -h\Delta T_{\text{surf}}$ of the top ($\Delta T_{\text{surf},1}$, $P_{\text{conv},1}$) and bottom sides ($\Delta T_{\text{surf},2}$, $P_{\text{conv},2}$) in units of [K] and [W/m²], respectively. These last four columns are valid for the median temperature profile and in our sign convention, a subcooled element has $\Delta T_{\text{surf}} < 0$, but $P_{\text{conv}} > 0$. In the above, "top" either indicates the upward surface closer to the sky, or, when considering a spider face, the *outside* of steel slab in a hollow spider

Fig 23 a,b) Monte Carlo simulation of ray end points from the sky through the dome slit directly onto the inner dome cladding (`rayOnDomeDirect`), using the "top-down" thermal ray tracing approach, seen from two different camera viewpoints. c) Similar to a,b), but for rays reflected off M1 before hitting the inner dome cladding (`rayOnDomeFromM1`). d) Ray path tally of all 50,000 sampled rays.

truss in contact with moving air. Conversely, "bottom" denotes the downward facing surface, or else the surface on the sealed inside of a rectangular truss with a correspondingly small h_2 .

For M2, we also simulate a speculative radiation shield above the top side of the mirror (i.e., $F_{\text{sky}} = 0$) and for the spiders, we consider the top vs. side faces and *LO/MIT-I* paint (non-Max with 23% emissivity) vs. *NanoBlack* foil (10% emissivity).

The table in Fig. 26 lists the same structural elements as Fig. 25, but yields blocks of the four quantities

$$\begin{array}{l} \Delta T_{\text{surf},1} \quad P_{\text{conv},1} \\ \Delta T_{\text{surf},2} \quad P_{\text{conv},2} \end{array}$$

Fig 24 Top: Five nocturnal ambient temperature profiles measured on Cerro Armazones and the reference profile (dashed). Bottom: As above, but vertically shifted to highlight the ambient temperature excursion relative to sunset.

System name	w	h1	h2	e	F_sky	ΔT_{top}	ΔT_{bot}	Material	ΔT_{Surf1}	Pconv1	ΔT_{Surf2}	Pconv2
M1 baseline	0.05	1.5	0.5	0.03	0.4	0.	0.5	Zerodur	-3.02895	4.54343	-3.04616	1.52308
M2 baseline, h(back wind)	0.1	1.8	3.46154	0.9	0.375	0.	0.	Zerodur	-7.86656	14.1598	-6.37785	22.0772
M2 baseline, h(lateral wind)	0.1	2.6	5.	0.9	0.375	0.	0.	Zerodur	-6.92384	18.002	-5.36074	26.8037
M2 baseline, h(lateral wind)-1	0.1	3.75556	7.22222	0.9	0.375	0.	0.	Zerodur	-5.8777	22.074	-4.26116	30.775
M2 with radiation shield, h(lateral wind)	0.1	2.6	5.	0.9	0.	0.	0.	Zerodur	-2.21123	5.7492	-2.05255	10.2627
M2 mount top (steel slab), h(lateral wind)	0.014	2.7	0.25	0.3	0.9	0.	0.	mild steel	-7.88774	21.2969	-7.88773	1.97193
M2 mount side (steel slab), h(lateral wind)	0.014	3.5	0.25	0.23	0.42	0.	0.	mild steel	-3.58967	12.5638	-3.59023	0.897557
M2 crown (steel slab), h(lateral wind)	0.014	5.9	0.25	0.23	0.5	0.	0.	mild steel	-2.72812	16.0959	-2.72898	0.682246
M3, h(lateral wind)	0.1	0.8	0.8	0.03	0.2	0.	0.	Zerodur	-3.12473	2.49978	-3.10988	2.4879
M4, h(lateral wind)	0.002	1.	0.25	0.03	0.2	0.	1.	Zerodur	-0.742216	0.742216	-0.742123	0.185531
Top Spider upper face, LO/MIT, h(back wind)	0.014	2.8	0.25	0.23	0.55	0.	0.	mild steel	-4.73538	13.2591	-4.73573	1.18393
Top Spider upper face, LO/MIT, h(lateral wind)	0.014	5.	0.25	0.23	0.55	0.	0.	mild steel	-3.31803	16.5901	-3.31877	0.829693
Top Spider upper face, LO/MIT, h(lateral wind)-2	0.014	7.	0.25	0.23	0.55	0.	0.	mild steel	-2.61545	18.3081	-2.61633	0.654081
Top Spider side face, LO/MIT, h(back wind)	0.02	2.4	0.25	0.23	0.39	0.	0.	mild steel	-4.23505	10.1641	-4.23554	1.05889
Top Spider side face, LO/MIT, h(lateral wind)	0.02	4.2	0.25	0.23	0.39	0.	0.	mild steel	-3.32182	13.9516	-3.32306	0.830765
Top Spider side face, LO/MIT, h(lateral wind)-2	0.02	6.	0.25	0.23	0.39	0.	0.	mild steel	-2.66131	15.9679	-2.66299	0.665747
Top Spider upper face, NanoBlack, h(back wind)	0.014	2.8	0.25	0.1	0.55	0.	0.	mild steel	-3.14631	8.80966	-3.14685	0.786714
Top Spider upper face, NanoBlack, h(lateral wind)	0.014	5.	0.25	0.1	0.55	0.	0.	mild steel	-2.30162	11.5081	-2.30246	0.575614
Top Spider upper face, NanoBlack, h(lateral wind)-2	0.014	7.	0.25	0.1	0.55	0.	0.	mild steel	-1.78266	12.4786	-1.78363	0.445908
Top Spider side face, NanoBlack, h(back wind)	0.02	2.4	0.25	0.1	0.39	0.	0.	mild steel	-3.21694	7.72065	-3.21771	0.804428
Top Spider side face, NanoBlack, h(lateral wind)	0.02	4.2	0.25	0.1	0.39	0.	0.	mild steel	-2.52845	10.6195	-2.52984	0.632461
Top Spider side face, NanoBlack, h(lateral wind)-2	0.02	6.	0.25	0.1	0.39	0.	0.	mild steel	-1.97753	11.8652	-1.97932	0.494831
Outside dome cladding, upper region	0.003	8.5	0.1	0.3	0.9	0.	0.	Al 6082	-3.15925	26.8536	-3.15925	0.315925
Roof of aux-entrance-hall (topview)	0.003	4.9	0.1	0.3	0.15	0.	0.	Al 6082	-1.0051	4.92497	-1.0051	0.10051
VLT M1	0.175	1.5	0.5	0.03	0.5	0.	0.5	Zerodur	-3.2997	4.94955	-3.32967	1.66483

Fig 25 Table of simulation parameters for several structural elements under various environmental conditions, configurations and convection coefficients. Last four columns: surface temperature offsets and convected powers.

for all six T_{amb} curves of Fig. 4 (with references to their respective colors). The strong dependence of air cooling on ambient temperature profiles, orientation to sky and cladding material is obvious. For example, the row labeled "Top Spider side face, NanoBlack, h(back wind)" shows convected powers between heating the passing air by 3.2 W/m^2 and cooling it with 8.7 W/m^2 . Note also the low temperatures and strong cooling powers on the M2 top (i.e., sky) side in the baseline configuration.

8.3 Thermal ray tracing analysis

Figure 27 shows the accumulated OPL along 12 cuts, each of the central part of length 1 m, running perpendicular to and across the spiders, for the simulation with full cladding (CASE02). The lateral ray density is 1 mm. The location of the cuts ("groups") in the pupil is indicated in the inset. In the top graph, the different color dots represent the accumulated OPL up to the mirrors M1, M2, . . . , M6, respectively. We can see that the curves for M2 almost overlap with those of the subsequent mirrors, hence, there is only little thermal OPL added, at least near the spiders, after the rays reflect off M2.

Since both, the subcooling temperature differences ΔT and dn/dT are negative, their product becomes positive, hence the side of the spider with the higher curve and the taller OPL spike is generally the downwind side.

The bottom group of plots show accumulated OPL up to M6 (i.e., through the entire beam train) for the three CFD simulation time steps of $t = 0, 60$ s and 120 s, which we consider mutually decoupled and thus statistically uncorrelated. One can see significant fluctuations in the OPL step height and slope. However, the asymmetry direction generally prevails. We conclude that DTS introduces a time scale of a few to tens of seconds into the AO control problem of ESO's ELT.

We can observe the following types of features:

- OPL "divergence" spikes next to the spider surfaces with a width of a few tens of millimeters,
- Even when ignoring the spikes, OPL jumps of up to ~ 300 nm across the spiders (400 nm in Group 6),
- Large differences in OPL slopes (e.g., in Groups 9 and 11).

Figure 28 c) shows temperatures and the accumulated OPL along rays crossing a cut running perpendicular to a spider. The spiders have a clear signature with a significant temperature and OPL spread across the ray bundle. M1 is slightly heated by residual dissipated power within the M1 Cell, while M2 is subcooled on its top side, inducing cool mirror seeing. We note that heating the upward facing primary mirror, and cooling the downward facing secondary, both generate boundary layers that tend to lift off the respective mirrors due to buoyancy. Hence, there is a possibility that the impact of these layers is less persistent, and hence severe, than of a cooled primary or a heated secondary, instead.

We currently ignore the segment gaps in M1 of 4 mm width with the associated air flow passing through them and, importantly, we do not model any missing segments, limiting the level of detail of M1 mirror seeing, in particular under back wind conditions. Moreover, we do not consider any variations of wind speed during the night, or the fact that nights with the best seeing often coincide with low wind speeds. More studies will be needed to elucidate these aspects.

An immediate consequence of the large-scale cooling resulting from Fig. 23 is that the air temperature inside the dome is globally lowered by about 0.1 K relative to ambient (CASE02). This temperature offset induces a corresponding overall change in OPL, but because it is so evenly distributed, it excites only low spatial orders whose OPD, presumably, can be easily corrected by the DMs. However, the associated field effect remains to be studied.

T_{amb} Profile (color curve) → Structural Element ↓	magenta (best)	blue	red	green	cyan (worst)	black dashed (median)
M1 baseline	2.98 -3.64 3.06 -1.53	1.12 -1.37 1.18 -0.59	0.35 -0.42 0.39 -0.2	-0.76 0.93 -0.73 0.37	-3.19 3.89 -3.19 1.6	0.93 -1.13 0.98 -0.49
M2 baseline, h(back wind)	-3.59 5.52 -2.08 5.48	-4.55 7.01 -3.09 8.15	-5.65 8.71 -4.13 10.91	-6.61 10.18 -5.13 13.54	-8.3 12.78 -6.91 18.24	-5.38 8.29 -3.82 10.08
M2 baseline, h(lateral wind)	-3.15 8.76 -1.6 9.34	-3.78 10.52 -2.25 13.09	-4.54 12.62 -2.89 16.85	-5.2 14.46 -3.55 20.7	-6.62 18.39 -4.97 29.	-4.39 12.21 -2.71 15.83
M2 baseline, h(lateral wind)+1	-2.77 11.87 -1.26 10.61	-3.21 13.77 -1.71 14.43	-3.75 16.09 -2.14 17.99	-4.3 18.45 -2.68 22.57	-5.52 23.7 -3.89 32.72	-3.69 15.84 -2.05 17.24
M2 with radiation shield, h(lateral wind)	2.17 -6.04 1.98 -11.57	1.06 -2.96 0.97 -5.64	0.59 -1.65 0.55 -3.18	-0.24 0.67 -0.23 1.32	-2.16 6.01 -1.98 11.53	0.94 -2.6 0.86 -4.99
M2 mount top (steel slab), h(back wind)	-6.38 11.29 -6.38 1.59	-6.81 12.06 -6.81 1.7	-7.58 13.41 -7.58 1.89	-8.39 14.85 -8.39 2.1	-9.51 16.83 -9.51 2.38	-7.19 12.72 -7.19 1.8
M2 mount top (steel slab), h(lateral wind)	-5.88 12.87 -5.88 1.47	-6.29 13.78 -6.29 1.57	-6.97 15.26 -6.97 1.74	-7.74 16.96 -7.74 1.94	-8.65 18.95 -8.65 2.16	-6.59 14.42 -6.58 1.65
M2 mount side (steel slab), h(back wind)	-1.04 2.14 -1.04 0.26	-1.77 3.64 -1.77 0.44	-2.33 4.79 -2.33 0.58	-3.19 6.57 -3.19 0.8	-4.8 9.88 -4.8 1.2	-2.21 4.56 -2.21 0.55
M2 mount side (steel slab), h(lateral wind)	-0.97 2.79 -0.97 0.24	-1.63 4.71 -1.63 0.41	-1.93 5.57 -1.93 0.48	-2.65 7.66 -2.65 0.66	-3.93 11.36 -3.93 0.98	-1.87 5.41 -1.87 0.47
M2 crown (steel slab), h(back wind)	-1.36 4.25 -1.36 0.34	-1.95 6.08 -1.95 0.49	-2.38 7.44 -2.38 0.6	-3.08 9.6 -3.08 0.77	-4.28 13.35 -4.28 1.07	-2.21 6.89 -2.21 0.55
M2 crown (steel slab), h(lateral wind)	-1.05 5.42 -1.05 0.26	-1.4 7.21 -1.4 0.35	-1.64 8.43 -1.64 0.41	-2.16 11.13 -2.16 0.54	-3. 15.47 -3. 0.75	-1.57 8.09 -1.57 0.39
M3, h(lateral wind)	4.02 -3.22 4.06 -3.25	1.78 -1.42 1.8 -1.44	0.97 -0.78 0.99 -0.79	-0.35 0.28 -0.33 0.26	-3.12 2.5 -3.11 2.49	1.58 -1.26 1.6 -1.28
M4, h(lateral wind)	-0.02 0.02 -0.02 0.	-0.23 0.23 -0.23 0.06	-0.11 0.11 -0.11 0.03	-0.41 0.41 -0.41 0.1	-0.74 0.74 -0.74 0.19	-0.2 0.2 -0.2 0.05
Top Spider upper face, LO/MIT, h(back wind)	-1.54 5.44 -1.54 0.38	-2.01 7.1 -2.01 0.5	-2.42 8.54 -2.42 0.6	-3.16 11.15 -3.16 0.79	-4.22 14.91 -4.22 1.06	-2.18 7.71 -2.18 0.55
Top Spider upper face, LO/MIT, h(lateral wind)	-1.27 6.4 -1.27 0.32	-1.64 8.25 -1.64 0.41	-1.86 9.35 -1.86 0.47	-2.39 11.99 -2.39 0.6	-3.3 16.55 -3.3 0.82	-1.71 8.57 -1.71 0.43
Top Spider upper face, LO/MIT, h(lateral wind)+2	-0.99 6.93 -0.99 0.25	-1.28 8.99 -1.28 0.32	-1.32 9.24 -1.32 0.33	-1.81 12.68 -1.81 0.45	-2.62 18.31 -2.62 0.65	-1.3 9.11 -1.3 0.33
Top Spider side face, LO/MIT, h(back wind)	-0.01 0.03 -0.01 0.	-1.09 3.33 -1.09 0.27	-1.58 4.84 -1.58 0.4	-2.34 7.15 -2.33 0.58	-3.92 11.98 -3.92 0.98	-1.45 4.43 -1.45 0.36
Top Spider side face, LO/MIT, h(lateral wind)	-0.14 0.58 -0.14 0.04	-0.94 3.79 -0.94 0.24	-1.29 5.18 -1.29 0.32	-1.99 8. -1.99 0.5	-3.37 13.55 -3.37 0.84	-1.28 5.15 -1.28 0.32
Top Spider side face, LO/MIT, h(lateral wind)+2	-0.19 1.15 -0.19 0.05	-0.87 5.2 -0.87 0.22	-0.88 5.26 -0.88 0.22	-1.52 9.12 -1.52 0.38	-2.66 15.97 -2.66 0.67	-1.01 6.04 -1.01 0.25
Top Spider upper face, NanoBlack, h(back wind)	0.14 -0.5 0.14 -0.04	-0.57 2.01 -0.57 0.14	-0.85 3.01 -0.85 0.21	-1.47 5.19 -1.47 0.37	-2.71 9.58 -2.71 0.68	-0.71 2.52 -0.71 0.18
Top Spider upper face, NanoBlack, h(lateral wind)	-0.03 0.16 -0.03 0.01	-0.46 2.29 -0.46 0.11	-0.6 3.01 -0.6 0.15	-1.16 5.85 -1.16 0.29	-2.25 11.3 -2.25 0.56	-0.56 2.81 -0.56 0.14
Top Spider upper face, NanoBlack, h(lateral wind)+2	-0.08 0.55 -0.08 0.02	-0.38 2.63 -0.38 0.09	-0.38 2.69 -0.38 0.1	-0.86 6. -0.86 0.21	-1.78 12.48 -1.78 0.45	-0.42 2.94 -0.42 0.1
Top Spider side face, NanoBlack, h(back wind)	1.03 -3.15 1.03 -0.26	0.13 -0.38 0.13 -0.03	-0.37 1.14 -0.37 0.09	-1.23 3.78 -1.23 0.31	-2.86 8.74 -2.86 0.71	-0.17 0.52 -0.17 0.04
Top Spider side face, NanoBlack, h(lateral wind)	0.82 -3.31 0.82 -0.21	0.16 -0.63 0.16 -0.04	-0.29 1.17 -0.29 0.07	-1.01 4.08 -1.01 0.25	-2.54 10.2 -2.54 0.63	-0.18 0.74 -0.18 0.05
Top Spider side face, NanoBlack, h(lateral wind)+2	0.5 -2.99 0.5 -0.12	-0.05 0.28 -0.05 0.01	-0.21 1.24 -0.21 0.05	-0.77 4.65 -0.78 0.19	-1.98 11.87 -1.98 0.49	-0.17 1.04 -0.17 0.04
Outside dome cladding, upper region	-3.53 30.03 -3.53 0.35	-4.34 36.91 -4.34 0.43	-4.13 35.07 -4.13 0.41	-3.41 29.01 -3.41 0.34	-3.16 26.85 -3.16 0.32	-3.24 27.54 -3.24 0.32
Roof of aux-entrance-hall (topview)	-0.72 3.52 -0.72 0.07	-0.83 4.09 -0.83 0.08	-0.8 3.93 -0.8 0.08	-0.93 4.54 -0.93 0.09	-1.01 4.92 -1.01 0.1	-0.81 3.98 -0.81 0.08
VLT M1	4.01 -6.01 4.39 -2.2	1.58 -2.37 1.87 -0.94	0.79 -1.19 1. -0.5	-0.61 0.91 -0.45 0.22	-3.3 4.95 -3.33 1.66	1.44 -2.15 1.66 -0.83

Fig 26 Table of 2×2 blocks of surface temperature offsets and convected powers $\Delta T_{surf,1}$, $P_{conv,1}$ atop $\Delta T_{surf,2}$, $P_{conv,2}$.

Fig 27 Top: OPL for each mirror along 12 cuts perpendicular to the spiders, accumulated to the mirrors M1–M6 (all for CASE02). Inset: Pupil with labels 1–12 and three of the six spiders for illustration. The OPD spikes and offsets, but also their different slopes, across the spiders are clearly visible.

Bottom: Same, but for the CFD time steps $t = 0, 60$ s and 120 s; OPD accumulated to M6.

Fig 28 a) Pupil sketch with M1 segments and one spider leg. The green lines indicate perpendicular cuts, of which study the rays passing the top one. b) Ray path in side view with spider and M1 cross-section. c) Temperatures along a ray bundle in the cut with the arrow (the violet zig-zag line indicates the vertical coordinate z along the ray).

Fig 29 Accumulated OPL along the ray bundle highlighted in Fig. 28

Fig 30 Side Wind: OPD map and RMS error

Fig 31 Side Wind: Fitting error RMS

Fig 32 Side Wind: Discontinuities, PTV and RMS

Fig 33 Back Wind: OPD map and RMS error

Fig 34 Back Wind: Fitting error RMS

Fig 35 Back Wind: Discontinuities, PTV and RMS